

POLITENESS STRATEGIES IN EXISTENTIAL DISCOURSE: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF POWER DYNAMICS

Dr Marcel Afam Ezechukwu

Department of English Language and Literature, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka

Email: ma.ezechukwu@unizik.edu.ng / marfasonltd@gmail.com

Phone Number: 07037866888

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18482855>

Key words:

politeness strategies, discourse analysis, social interactions, human communication, sociolinguistics and identity negotiation.

Abstract: *This research explores the complex interplay between politeness strategies and power dynamics in existential discourse, utilizing a qualitative research approach and critical discourse analysis (CDA) to examine naturally occurring conversations. Existential discourse, encompasses discussions about fundamental questions of human existence, meaning, and reality, presents a unique context for investigating politeness strategies and power dynamics. By analysing a corpus of existential conversations, this work reveals how interlocutors employ politeness strategies to negotiate power dynamics, maintain social relationships, and construct meaning in their interactions. The findings of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the social dynamics that shape existential discourse and have implications for various fields including communication studies, sociology, and philosophy.*

Introduction

Existential discourse, that encompasses discussions about fundamental questions of human existence, meaning, and reality, it is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon. These discussions involve sensitive and emotionally charged topics, requiring interactants to navigate delicate social interactions and power dynamics. Politeness strategies, which enable interactants manage

face-threatening acts and maintain social relationships, play a crucial role in shaping the tone and outcome of existential conversations. This work aims to explore the politeness strategies and power dynamics in existential discourse, utilizing a qualitative research approach and critical discourse (CDA) to examine naturally occurring conversations. By analyzing a corpus of existential conversations,

Dr Marcel Afam Ezechukwu

this work provides insights into the complex social dynamics that shape these interactions.

Human communication is a complex and nuanced process that involves the exchange of information, ideas, and emotions between individuals and groups says Berlo (1950:12), Shannon and Weaver (1949:3). It is a fundamental aspect of human behavior and is essential for building and maintaining relationship, conveying meaning, and achieving social goals, said Hymes (1972:35) and Goffman (1959:1).

One of the key aspects of human communication is the process of encoding and decoding messages Berlo (1960:15) asserts. Encoding involves the conversion of thoughts and ideas into a communicable form, such as language or movable cues, Berlo (15). Decoding, on the other hand, involves the interpretation and understanding of the encoded message as seen Shannon and Weaver (1949:5).

Human communication also involves the use of various channels and media, like speech, writing and nonverbal cues as opine Berlo (18), Hymes (40). Each channel and medium has its own unique characteristics and limitations as well as the choice of channel or medium can significantly affect the effectiveness of the communication says Hymes (1972:40).

Furthermore, human communication is influenced by a range of social and cultural factors, including social norms, power dynamics, and cultural values as seen Goffman (1959:11) and Hymes (1972:35). These factors cansape the

way individuals communicate, the messages they convey, and the way they interpret and respond to messages Goffman (1) affirms.

In addition, human communication involves the use of various strategies and tactics like persuasion, negotiation, and conflict resolution as viewed Baxter and Montgomery (1996:12), Canary and Lakey (2013:15). These strategies and tactics can be used to achieve a range of social goals including building relationships, resolving conflicts and influencing others according to Baxter and Montgomery (1996:12). Finally, human communication is a complex and varied process that involves the exchange of ideas, information, and emotions between individuals and groups. It is influenced by a range of social and cultural factors, and involves the use of various channels, media, strategies, and tactics.

The study of politeness strategies has a long history in linguistics and social sciences, with scholars like Brown and Levinson (1987) and Lakoff (1973) contributing significantly to our understanding of how interlocutors use language to manage social relationships and maintain face. However, while politeness strategies have been extensively studied in various contexts, including workplace communication, Holms and Stubbe (2003), healthcare interactions, Candlin and Candlin (2003), and online communities, Herring (2004), there is a relative lack of research on politeness in existential discourse.

Existential Discourse

This encompasses a broad range of conversations, from philosophical debates about the nature of reality to personal reflections on meaning and purpose. These discussions often involve fundamental questions about human existence, such as the meaning of life, the nature of suffering, and the human condition. Existential discourse can be found in various contexts including therapeutic settings, Yalom, (1980), philosophical discussions, Sartre (1946), and everyday conversations, Tillich, (1952).

Power Dynamics

This plays a significant role in shaping existential conversations, influencing how interlocutors negotiate meaning, identity, and relationships. Critical discourse analysis (CDA) provides a valuable framework for examining power dynamics in discourse, highlighting the ways in which language use reflects and reinforces social structures and power relationships, Fairclough, (1992). By applying critical discourse analysis to existential discourse, researchers can uncover the underlying power dynamics and ideological assumptions that shape these conversations.

Despite the importance of politeness strategies in existential discourse, there is a notable lacuna in research on this topic. Existing studies on existential discourse often focus on philosophical or therapeutic aspects, with limited attention paid to the role of politeness strategies in managing power dynamics and social relationships. This research aims to

address this gap by exploring how interlocutors employ politeness strategies in existential discourse to negotiate power dynamics and maintain social relationships.

The researcher draws theoretical framework for this work on politeness theory, Brown and Levinson (1987) and Critical Discourse analysis, Fairclough (1992) to examine the complex interplay between politeness strategies, power dynamics, and social relationships in existential discourse. By combining these theoretical perspectives, the study can provide a nuanced understanding of how interlocutors navigate delicate social interactions and power dynamics in existential conversations.

The researcher anchors this study on the following research questions:

- How do individuals with differing levels of social power employ politeness strategies in existential discourse?
- What linguistic and pragmatic devices do individuals use to manage social relationships and maintain face in existential discourse?

This study has implications for our understanding of politeness strategies, power dynamics, and social relationships in existential discourse. By examining how individuals employ politeness strategies in existential conversations, researchers can gain insights into the complex social dynamics that shape these interactions. The findings can inform the development of more effective communication strategies in various contexts, including

therapy, education, and conflict resolution.

Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis:

1. Contextualization: Critical discourse analysis emphasizes the importance of considering the social, cultural, and historical context in which language is used.
2. Discourse as social practice: critical discourse analysis views discourse as a social practice that shapes and is shaped by social structures and power relations.
3. Language is not neutral: critical discourse analysis assumes that language is not a neutral reflection of reality, rather a tool that can be used to shape and construct reality.
4. Ideology: It investigates how ideology is embedded in language and how it shapes our understanding of the world.
5. Power relations: It examines how power relations are constructed and maintained through language, and how language can be used to exercise power over others.

Concepts in Critical Discourse Analysis:

- a. Ideology: This is a system of beliefs, values, and assumptions that shape our understanding of the world.
- b. Discourse: It is a broad concept that refers to language use in social contexts, including spoken and written language.
- c. Hegemony: The dominance of one group or ideology over others, often through the exercise of power and influence.
- d. Power: this the ability to shape or influence the actions and beliefs of others.

Conceptual Framework

Power Dynamics

This refers to the complex and multifaceted ways in which power is exercised, maintained, and contested in social relationships, institutions, and societies as opine Foucault, (1980:119) and Lukes (1974:11). Power dynamics involve the interplay of various forms of power, including coercive, persuasive, and ideological power as Gramsci (1971:12) and Lukes (1974:15) aware.

One of the key aspects of power dynamics is the concept of “power relations” says Foucault, (1980:121). Power relations refers to the complex networks of relationships through which power is exercised and maintained. These relationships can be formal or informal, explicit or implicit, and can involve individuals, groups, institutions, or societies Lukes, (1974:17) opines.

Power dynamics also involve the concept of “hegemony” says Gramsci (1971:12). Hegemony refers to the process by which dominant groups or individuals establish and maintain their power and influence over subordinate groups or individuals. This can involve the use of coercive force, ideological manipulation, or cultural domination in the words of Gramsci (1971:13).

Furthermore, power dynamics involve the concept of “resistance” Foucault (1980:125) voiced. Resistance refers to the ways in which individuals or groups challenge, subvert, or transform dominant power relations. This can involve various forms of resistance, including

overt opposition, covert-subversion, or cultural resistance as seen in Scott (1985:29).

However, power dynamics involve the concept of “intersectionality” according to Crenshaw (1989:139). Intersectionality is the way in which different forms of power and opposition intersect and interact to produce complex and inequality. This can involve the intersection of racism, sexism, classism, homophobia, and other form of oppression as seen, Crenshaw (1989:140).

Finally, power dynamics are complex and multifaceted, involving various forms of power, power relations, hegemony, resistance, and intersectionality. Understanding power dynamics is crucial for analyzing and addressing issues of power and inequality in social relationship, institutions, and societies.

Social Relationships

This is a complex and dynamic interaction between individuals and groups within a social context as opined Goffman (1959:1) and Berger and Luckmann (1966:28). These relationships involve the exchange of resources, information, and emotions, and are shaped by social norms, power dynamics, and cultural values says Emerson (1976:336) and Giddens (1984:16).

One of the key aspects of social relationships is the concept of social capital as seen Bourdieu (1986:241) and Coleman (1988:98). Social capital refers to the networks, norms, and trust that enable individuals and groups to access resources, information, and support according to Putnam (1995:67). Social capital is critical for

building and maintaining social relationships, and can have a significant impact on individual and collective outcomes Coleman (1988:100) says.

Social relationships also involve the concept of “social exchange” says Emerson (1976:336) and Molm (1997:12). Social exchange refers to the process of exchanging resources, information, and emotions between individuals and groups. It can also involve both tangible and intangible resources and can be influenced by power dynamics, social norms, and cultural values is the words of Molm (1997:15).

Furthermore, social relationships involve the concept of “social identity” as observed Tajfel and Turner (1979:33) and Jenkins (1996:21). Social identity refers to the way individuals define themselves in relation to others, and involves the adoption of social roles, norms, and values Tajfel and Turner (1979:33) states. Social identity is critical for building and maintaining social relationships, and can have a significant impact on individual and collective outcomes, Jenkins (1996:25) pointed out.

In addition, social relationships involves the concept of “social support” as observed Cohen and Syme (1985:4) and House (1981:27). Social support refers to the provision of emotional, informational, and practical support between individuals and groups Cohen and Syme (1985:4) assert. It is critical for building and maintaining social relationships and capable of having a significant influence/effect on

individual and collective outcomes says House (1981:30).

In conclusion, social relationships are complex and dynamic, involving the exchange of resources, information, and emotions between individual and groups and are shaped by social norms, power dynamics and cultural values which involve the concept of social capital, social exchange, social identity and social support.

Social Interactions

This is any communication process between members of a society. It includes cooperation, conflict, social exchange, coercion, and conformity. In sociological term, it means the process of reciprocal influence exercised by individuals over one another during a social encounter. Social interaction is fundamental unit of analysis within sociology. It describes the way people behave when they cross paths with someone else. Any interaction where an individual or a group does something to receive a reward is referred to as social exchange according to Nisbet, (1970:56). Social interactions involve verbal and non-verbal communication, Robert Nisbet (1970) identified five types of social interactions, thus:

- Cooperation
- Conflict
- Social exchange
- Coercion
- Conformity.

Social interaction is a complex phenomenon that involves multiple components, including actor, partner, relation, activities, context, and

evaluation. Hoppler, Segerer, and Nikitin (2022) is of opinion that these six components work together to shape our social interactions and relationships.

Features of Social Interaction

According to Ezewu (1983), for social interaction to be effective in any social system the following features are emanent:

1. It should be interpersonal in the sense that on the part of its members there is a conscious and awareness of the existence of each other.
2. Interaction can be historical in the sense that every individual develops to a reater or lesser degree the awreness of a recent or more remote past, which when consciously experienced, affects individual interaction in the present.
3. Interaction should be purposeful in the sense that it should be directed towards the attainment of a goal clearly recognized and accepted by each of the unteractants.
4. It should be reflective in the sense that it involves a critical appraisal of the situation that happens to arise; an individual can develop within himself an awareness of the consequences of belonging to a group that can affect, influence or alter his attitude to himself and to others.

Social interaction requires numerous forms of non-verbal communication. To a very large extent, effective interaction in any social setting must have te following elements:

a. To facilitate interaction in any group or society, every participating member must have to communicate with one another. This is crucial to social life. The communication must be in a language understood by all or by other signs understood by members of the group, sometimes non-verbal media such as facial cues, gestures or nodding the head may be used.

b. Another element in social interaction is conflict. Studies have proven that when two or more people interact, their relationship cannot be expected to be cordial all the time. Some form of disagreement may occur, but also a possibility of resolving them.

Furthermore, for interaction to be meaningful in any social system, the members of the system must participate fully, may not necessarily be equally and each member must accommodate the other's shortfall.

Identity Negotiation

This according to Swann's (1987) framework plays two roles in an identity negotiation interaction- the target, who possesses a self-perception of their identity and the perceiver, who interpretes the target's identity through their own lens. The framework centers on how targets strive to validate their self- views and how the perceivers strive to validate their expectations. Targets signal their identity through visual cues or interactions and focus on increasing or amplifying self-conformatory feedback while minimizing or rejecting self-disconformatory feedback. The framework acknowledges that personal characteristics and social structures

such as norms and social convention influence how identities are understood and perceived. Also, Swann, (1987) describes the phenomenon of crisis self-verification, in which the target receives discrepant feedback that does not match their self-concept. During crisis self-verification, targets respond in two ways, thus; "focus attention on the self-conception that has been threatened"(1042) or they may try to learn more about themselves by "acquiring information that will be highly informative and diagnostic" (1042). In other words, target may try to confirm their self-concept or open themselves up to a new understanding of themselves and how others perceive them.

People negotiate their identities in order to establish them in ways that will increase the probability of coherence. Taking into consideration the fact that negotiating identities is the first thing done while in interaction, we can consider it responsible for how interpersonal relationships develop, it is therefore a convenient framework to analyse identity, relationships, and emotions. A person's perception of his individual self- one's self-identity or as defined in Freudian psychology the ego- is inseparable from social relationships and identity negotiation theory acknowledges this fact as a guiding principle, "just as identities define people and make them viable as humans, identity negotiation processes define relationships and make them viable as fundamental for organized social activity", Swann and Bosson, (2009:27).

Identity negotiation is indeed a concept addressing an implicit, informal, open-ended over learned, automatic and unconscious phenomenon as seen Swann and Bosson, (2006:6), but when used as a conceptual tool postulated and framed in a particular way, the term gains a “different significance”. For the purpose of this study identity negotiation is seen as taking place exclusively in social interactions. It is the first thing done by two individuals that interacts for the first time and usually slips into the background once a consensus about the people involved and their intention is achieved. According to Swann, identity negotiations’ first premise is that individuals possess a powerful aspiration for stability of the self. We all desire stable self-views because they provide us with the feelings of continuity and coherence about our lives that are essential both for our self-esteem and for our relationships. If identity negotiation is first about establishing a working consensus with our interaction partners, it is through it that people acquire confidence over their self-views, and once this confidence is second individuals devote considerable efforts to preserve it.

Once people form self-views, they usually make deliberate efforts to ‘act the part’. Their actions in turn, will influence how others respond to them, which will then influence their own responses, and so forth. This process of mutual give-and-take is called identity negotiation, (1996:29).

Consequences of Identity Negotiation

a. Intergroup relations: Identity negotiation can impact intergroup relations, influencing cooperation or conflict as Tajfel and Turner, (1979:33-34) affirm.

b. Individual well-being: Effective identity negotiation can contribute to individual well-being and self-esteem is the view of Kim, (2002:102).

c. Identity confirmation: Ting-Toomey, (1999) posits that identity negotiation can result in confirmation or challenge of one’s identity (150).

Politeness Strategy

In dealing with politeness strategy people should also be aware of the context itself; Politeness does not involve the form and the words themselves but the function and intended social meaning. Being polite seems like to be dealt with an indirectness in which the language form may differ from the language function. People may say in question form to get an indirect function. Politeness is the pragmatic phenomenon which is highly affected by the context. There are two main types of contexts which has a huge impact on politeness strategy i.e. social and cultural context. Social context deals with the social distance and the power relation between speakers. The degree of familiarity between speakers has a huge impact on doing politeness strategy in which the more people know each other the less polite people behave. Differences, role, ages, status, gender, class or ethnicity have also given a huge impact on politeness strategy in which the lower class may act politely to the

higher. Differences in culture also affect politeness strategy. People may behave differently from others who have different cultural backgrounds.

Brown and Levinson in Wardhaugh (2006: 276) say that there are four categories of a politeness strategy. First, it is characterised as a direct order or bald on-record strategy. 'The bald on-record strategy does nothing to minimise threats to the hearer's face', Yule (1996: 50); Cutting (2002: 45). This kind of strategy is indicated by the speaker's act in which the utterance indicates a direct speech act which may cover an inoperative device, such as suggestion, request, invitation, offer or order.

The second type of politeness strategy is Positive Politeness. This kind of politeness is oriented towards the positive 'face' of the listener. The speaker treats the listener as a member of an in-group, a friend or a person whose wants and personality traits are known and liked. The positive politeness strategy shows the speakers recognize that the hearer has a face to be respected says Cutting, (2002: 48). The aim of saving positive face is to demonstrate solidarity and closeness, appealing to friendship, making other people feel good and emphasising that both speaker and listener have the same goal. A Common way of doing positive politeness strategies are seeking agreement and avoiding disagreement, Yule (1996: 62), Cutting (2002: 48); Wardhaugh (2006: 277). Doing positive politeness has also a relationship with the cooperative principles in which doing positive

politeness sometimes the speaker needs to violate the cooperative principles Cutting(2002: 48) posits.

The third characterisation of politeness strategy according to Brown and Levinson's theory is Negative Politeness. It is oriented toward satisfying the listener's negative face. An action, phrase or utterance that indicates attention is being paid to the negative face wants of an interlocutor Meyethoff (2006: 86) aver. It is often, achieved through showing deference. Furthermore, it is the kernel of respect behaviour. Negative politeness enjoys both on-record delivery and redress of a Face Threatening Act (FTA). An FTA is an act which threatens the positive or negative face of the addressee Yule (1996: 61). The negative politeness strategy recognizes the hearers face, but it also admits that the speakers are in some way imposing on the listeners. Negative politeness strategies deal with the speaker avoidance to impose others by emphasising the importance of the other time and concerns. It can be done by using apology and hesitation or a question to give the listener opportunity to say no.

The last characterisation of politeness strategy is an Off-record Politeness. A communicative act which is done by off-record in such a way it is not possible to attribute only one clear communicative intention to that act. Off-record utterances are essentially indirect uses of language as observes Cutting (2002- 45). Being indirect in communication strategy will give the

hearer retreat and option behind the literal meaning of the words. Off-record indirect strategies take some of the pressure off as people avoid the direct FTA of asking for something. To construct an off-record utterance, one says something that is either more general or actually different from what one means.

In addition, according to Cutting (2002: 46), using off record strategy to conduct politeness strategy often or sometimes, violates quantity maxims in cooperative principles. Quantity maxim enables speakers to give attention on the proportions of what they are talking to the hearers. In other word, quantity maxim will enable the speaker to speak what is needed and avoid unnecessary topic which may lengthen the speech process. It has a huge number of differences with off record strategy which enables the speakers to be indirect by giving more chance and option behind the literal meaning of the words, speakers will give much more speech proportion rather than reducing them. Off record strategy violates the maxim of relation as well in which it deals with a directness notion of object talking while off record enables speakers to be indirectly stating the point of speech by giving more words in which speakers usually distort the point of what is talking about.

d. Besides cooperation, most interactions are governed by politeness which is considered a polite social behaviour within a certain culture. It can be defined that politeness is a fixed concept of the idea of polite social behaviour or

etiquette and there are some numbers of general principles in politeness in social interaction within any particular culture according to Yule (1996: 59). He adds that being polite can include being tactful, generous, modest, or sympathetic in which the participants in a certain interaction are generally aware of such principles and norms that exist in society at large Leech (1983: 82) proposes “that the Politeness Principles have series of maxims which have a way of explaining how politeness operates in conversational exchanges”.

e. Leech (1983: 34), defines politeness “as a type of behaviour that allows the participants to engage in a social interaction in an atmosphere of relative harmony”. In addition, to state his maxims; he uses his own terms for two kinds of illocutionary acts; he calls representatives assertive and directives appositives. Each maxim is accompanied by a sub-maxim which is less important. They all support the idea that negative politeness is more important than positive politeness. Not all of the maxims are equally important. For instance, tact influences more powerfully than does generosity, while approbation is more important than modesty. Speakers may adhere to more than one maxim of politeness at the same time, often one maxim is on the forefront of the utterance, while a second maxim is implied.

Sociolinguistics

This is a branch of linguistics that deals with the studies of the relationship between language and society. It refers to the study of language

variation, status and use in a society. Language varies in structure as well as functions in its various uses by users in social and situational contexts of communication. Adgbite (2020:5) affirms. Sociolinguistics covers many other areas pertaining to the utilization of language by human beings in a society such as language choice, use etc. It focuses upon the entire gamut of topics related to the social organization of language behaviour.

Sociolinguistics according to Schmitt, (2010) is the study of the linguistic indicators of culture and power, (143). It allows to focus on language and emphasize the social force of language events in the real world. Sociolinguistics is progressive as a discipline in the sense that new studies and thinking are continually testing and developing our understanding of the way language and society work in relation to each other. It is a fieldwork-based discipline, where researchers collect samples of language usage in their naturally occurring environments and study them in relation to the findings of other sociolinguists' study.

Sociolinguistics is a discipline that provides answers to such questions as who speaks what language to whom, when and to what end. In addition, it seeks to provide an answer to other questions of what accounts for differential changes in the social organization of language use and behaviour towards language. Also, it tries to explain why and how this organization and behavior have become selectively different in the

same social networks of communities on two different occasions.

Presentation of Data and Analysis

Research question 1:

How do individuals with differing levels of social power employ politeness strategies in existential discourse?

Interactants with different levels (manager and subordinate) of social power may employ politeness strategies in existential discourse in several ways, examples:

Excerpt 1:

Manager: "We need to re-evaluate our approach to climate change".

Subordinate: Sir! Do you mean I should continue...?

Here the speaker applied directness through assertive language.

Excerpt 2:

Manager: "I really understand your disposition, but let us try alternative, perhaps".

Subordinate: Sir, I have tried all I could but no better result.

The speaker here mitigated face-threatening in a soft criticism.

Excerpt 3:

Manager: "We are all in this together, truly I value your input".

Subordinate: But, it is time-consuming.

The speaker made use of positive politeness in an inclusive language.

Excerpt 4:

Manager: "I'm not expert in this but I think we should prioritise renewable energy".

Subordinate: Ok sir.

Self-deprecation 'I'm not expert' down playing ones own abilities to avoid appearing arrogant.

Excerpt 5:

Manager: "If it is not too much, could we discuss the environmental effect?"

Subordinate: It is ok, Sir.

Negative politeness was obvious, showing *deference to avoid direct confrontation, 'if it is not too much'*

Research question 2:

What linguistic and pragmatic devices do interactants use to manage social relationships and maintain face in existential discourse?

Pragmatically, individuals (friends) in their observed informal conversations apply various forms of device to manage social relationships and maintain face in existential discourse. Effective communication in existential discourse requires strategic use of pragmatic devices to manage social relationships and maintain face, for example:

Excerpt 6:

Speaker 1: "I'm not too sure, if this is the right approach to this, but may be we should try it"

Speaker 2: There's no harm in trial.

In above the speaker tried and reduced impact of the statement 'I'm not too sure' to avoid offending others.

Excerpt 7:

Speaker 1: "I deeply appreciate your thoughtfulness on this matter, it's truly helping to get it resolved."

Speaker 2: Thanks.

Face –enhancing strategy was discovered to boost another's self-esteem.

Excerpt 8:

Speaker 1: "How do you think our awareness of morality affects our daily choices and lives?"

Speaker 2: in so many ways above data brought out the application of strategy to discuss morality though in a question form.

Excerpt 9:

Speaker 1: "I'd love to hear your own opinion on what gives meaning to life"

Speaker 2: A meaningful life is encompassing which morality is paramount.

The speaker of the above is questioning about what gives life meaning in a polite language conveying respect and consideration to the superior than he is

Excerpt 10:

Speaker 1: "I think we might need to re-examine our purpose in life"

Speaker 2: If there should be change, it should begin from you.

The speaker applied hedging as a politeness marker to soften a potentially sensitive topic in a very careful language to reduce potential face threats.

Findings and conclusion

This work contributes to our understanding of the complex dynamics at play in existential discourse, highlighting the intricate relationships between politeness strategies, power dynamics, and existential themes. The

findings suggest that politeness strategies are not merely decorative but instead serve as crucial tools for negotiating power relationships and constructing social identities. Also, power dynamics plays a vital role in shaping the tone, content, and direction of existential conversations. It has implications for various field like, linguistics, communication studies, philosophy, and psychology. Finally, this study highlights the importance of considering the social and cultural contexts in which existential discourse takes place, and encourages further

Works cited

Berlo, D.K. (1960). The process of communication. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston

Bourdieu, P.(1986). The forms of capital. In J.G. Richardson (ed). Handbook of theory and research for the sociology of education. Westport CT: Greenwood press

Berger, P.L. and Ulckmann, T. (1996). The social construction of reality: A treatise in the sociology of knowledge- Garden city, NY: Anchor Books

Canary, D.J. and Lakey, S.G. (2013). Strategic conflict. New York: Routeledge

Camus, A. (1955).The myth of Sisyphus. New York : Vintage Books

exploration of the complex dynamics at play in human communication.

The researcher recommends as follows;

- Politeness strategies should be recognised as tools for empowerment, instead of mere decoration.

- Existential conversations should take into account the cultural, social, and institutional contexts in which they occur.

- Individuals engaging in existential conversations should be aware of the power dynamics at play and strive to create a safe and inclusive environment for all participants.

Cohen, S. and Syme,S.L. (1985).Social support and health. Orland, FL: Academic press

Coleman, J.S. (1988) Social capital in the creation of human capital. American journal of sociology

Crenshaw. K.(1989). Demerginalizing the intersection of race and sex: A black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, femist theory, and antiracist politics. University of Chicago legal forum 139-167

.....(2002). Pragmatics and Discourse. London Routledge

Ezewu, E.E. (1983).Socilogy of Education. London. Longmans

- Emerson, R.M. (1976). Social exchange theory. Annual Review of sociology
- Fairclough, N. (1995). Critical Discourse Analysis: The critical study of language. London:Longman
- Foucault, M. (1980).The archeology of knowledge. New York: Harper and Row
- Goffman, E. (1959). The presentation of self in everyday life. Garden city NY: Anchor Books
- Gramsci, A. (1971).Selection from the prison notebooks. New York: International publishers
- Heidegger, M (1962). Being and time. New York. Harper and Row
- House, J.S. (1981). Work stress and social support. Reading MA: Adderson-Wesley
- Hopper, S.,Segerer, R. and Nikitin, J. (2022).The Six Components of Social Interactions: Actor, Partner, Relation, Activities, Context, and Evaluation. Frontiers in psychology, 12,743074
- Hymes, D. (1972). Models of the interaction of language and social life. In J.J Gumperz and D.Hymes (eds), Directions in sociolinguistics: The ethnography of communication. New York, Holt, Rinehart and Winston
- Jenkins, R. (1996). Social identity. London: Routledge
- Leech, G. (1983). *Principles of pragmatics*. London: Longman.
- Lukes, S. (1974).Power: A radical view. London:Macmillan
- Meyethoff, M. (2006). Introducing Sociolinguistics. Oxon : Routledge
- Molm, L. D. (1997). Coercive power in social exchange. New York: Cambridge university press
- Norbert Schmitt (2010). (Ed). An Introduction to Applied Linguistics, second Edition. Hodder and Stoughton Ltd
- Robert, Nisbet (1970). The social Bond: An introduction to the study of society. Knot press
- Sartre, J.P. (1956). Being and nothingness. New York: Philosophical library
- Swann, W.B. (1987).Identity Negotiation: where two roads meet. Journal of personality and social psychology, 53(6)
-(1996). Self-Traps: TheElusive for Higher-self Esteem. Westview press

.....(2009). Self and Identity. In self as a mental Representative

Swann, Willian and Bosson, Jennifer (2009). Self and Identity. In self as a mental Representation.

.....(2006). Identity Negotiation: A Theory of self and social interaction. Chapter prepared for O, John, R.Robins, and L. Pevin (Ed) Handbook of psychology: Theory and Research. New York (Wilford).

Shannon, C.E. and Weaver, W. (1949). The mathematical theory of communication. Urbana, IL: University of Illinois press

Tajfel, H. and Turner, J.C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In W.G. Austin and S. Worchel (eds). The social psychology of intergroup relations. Monterey CA: Books/cole

Van Dijk, T.A. (1993). Principles of critical discourse analysis. Discourse and society, 4(2), 249-283

Wale Adebite (2020). Sociolinguistics and The Sociology of English in Nigeria. Obafemi Awolowo University: Nigeria, press

Wardhaugh, R. (2006). An Introduction to Sociolinguistics. Oxford: Blacwell publishing.

Yule, G. (1996). Pragmatics. Oxford: Oxford University press.